

Immediate Implant Placement In Esthetic Zone - A Case Report

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Abstract

Immediate implant placement in the lower anterior region involves inserting a dental implant directly into the extraction socket immediately after tooth removal. This approach aims to preserve alveolar bone, reduce treatment time, and enhance esthetic outcomes. A 26 year old female patient presented with the primary concern of poor facial appearance while smiling due to the mobility of the lower central incisor. After evaluating the CBCT results, implant was planned for the patient. Immediate implantation helps prevent vertical tissue collapse around the implant, promotes the formation of keratinized tissue on all sides, and allows for easier apical anchorage. Early implant placement does have limitations, such as increased surgical time and complexity compared to immediate placement.

Keywords - Dental Implants, Cementoenamel junction, Immediate implant placement, Cone beam Computed Tomography, Esthetic Zone.

Introduction

Initially, it was recommended that dental implants be surgically placed at the planned site only after several months of healing following tooth extraction. This delay allowed for sufficient remodelling and healing of the alveolar bone, which was believed to enhance osseointegration of the implant^[1]. However, not long afterward, an alternative approach immediate implant placement (IIP) was introduced, involving the insertion of the implant directly into the alveolar socket immediately after tooth extraction^[2]. Compared to the traditional delayed protocol, IIP offers several benefits, including reduced overall treatment time, fewer surgical procedures, minimized post-extraction alveolar bone resorption, a positive psychological impact on the patient, and the potential to position the implant in an optimal axial alignment with the extracted tooth^[3].

The placement of implants into the alveolar socket right after tooth extraction is called immediate implant placement (IIP)^[4]. This approach has its particularities depending on which region of the jaws is involved. The anterior mandible region is peculiar due to the presence of mandibular incisors, which have the shortest roots among all permanent teeth. Immediate implant placement in the lower anterior region involves inserting a dental implant directly into the extraction socket immediately after tooth removal. This approach aims to preserve alveolar bone,

reduce treatment time, and enhance esthetic outcomes.

The Immediate implant placement approach has its particularities depending on which region of the jaws is involved. The anterior mandible region is peculiar due to the presence of mandibular incisors, which have the shortest roots among all permanent teeth^[5]. Having that in mind, it is important that an adequate pre-treatment evaluation is conducted in the cases which Immediate implant placement is planned^[6].

Proper positioning of the implant is essential to ensure long-term success. It is recommended to place the implant at least 1.5 mm from the buccal plate and 2 mm below the cemento-enamel junction (CEJ) of adjacent teeth. This positioning helps prevent implant thread exposure due to buccal plate resorption and allows space for bone grafting material if needed.

A study utilizing cone-beam computed tomography (CBCT) found that bone driven implant placement aligning the implant according to available bone and anatomical structures resulted in a higher rate of safe placements (22.2%) compared to prosthetically driven placement (3.3%). This suggests that prioritizing existing bone structure may

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reduce the risk of cortical bone perforation and proximity to vital anatomical features. When compared with the delayed implant placement protocol, early dental implant placement offers advantages in the preservation of soft and hard tissues [7]. In certain cases, immediate loading of the implant (attaching a prosthetic tooth shortly after placement) can be considered. Immediate implant placement in the mandibular esthetic zone is a viable treatment option that can lead to favourable outcomes when executed with meticulous planning and technique.

This case report presents a technique involving early implant placement with immediate loading in the mandibular anterior region. This method offers a prompt and effective solution, minimizing the potential for tissue loss while optimizing esthetics and functionality through careful case selection and precise surgical technique are imperative to ensure success.

Clinical Case Report

A 26 year old female patient presented to the Department of Periodontics, DJ College of Dental Sciences and Research, Modinagar with the primary concern of poor facial appearance while smiling due to the Mobility of the lower central incisor. The patient reported a history of trauma to the area few months back, which resulted in this. There was no other significant medical, family or dental history. Considering the patient's esthetic concerns in the anterior region and their preference, an implant based fixed prosthetic rehabilitation was planned. Oral prophylaxis was performed, and the patient was given detailed oral hygiene instructions. During follow-up visits, the patient's oral hygiene was found to be satisfactory. A diagnostic impression was made with irreversible hydrocolloid and poured in dental stone. The obtained cast was used for mock-up using acrylic tooth. After evaluating the CBCT results, implant was planned for the patient.

We followed the standard surgical protocol for early implant placement by Buser et al. [8, 9] in which their various publications were taken into consideration for better clinical outcomes. Informed as well as written consent was taken from the patient prior to the treatment. Anesthesia was achieved through the local infiltration of 2% Lignocaine HCl with 1:200,000 epinephrine. A midcrestal incision was performed using a suitable BP blade, and a full thickness mucoperiosteal flap was gently raised to visualize the available alveolar bone in both the mesiodistal and buccolingual directions. The soft tissue remnants from the implant surgical site were cleared and irrigated with normal saline. Subsequently, the osteotomy site preparation was performed with respect to tooth. Initial pilot drill of 2.0 mm from the implant surgical kit was used as the first drill. Next, a guide pin was placed into the osteotomy site to ensure its alignment parallel to the adjacent tooth which was confirmed with intraoral periapical radiograph. Final implant placement was then done, and again, intraoral periapical radiograph was taken. With temporary abutment in place, closed tray impression was made using putty and light body and sent to the lab for provisional crown fabrication. Healing cap was screwed into the implant. Jumping distance was filled with Xenografts, and two interrupted 3-0 silk sutures were placed. The patient was well informed about the possible risks associated with implant surgery. Mouthwash with 0.2% chlorhexidine gluconate (100 ml mouthwash) 10ml twice daily for 21 days was advised. Nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) (ibuprofen 400mg and paracetamol 375mg, as per need and antibiotics (Amoxicillin 500mg+clavulanic acid 125mg, three times a day for five days were prescribed to the patient. After provisional crown fabrication, occlusal adjustments were done so that no contact is

established with opposing teeth, and immediate loading was done. After one week following surgery, the patient was recalled for suture removal and evaluation of the surgical site. Regular follow-up visits at 2 and 3 months were scheduled for the patient. On re-evaluation during follow-up visits, soft tissue healing was found to be satisfactory. The patient was then recalled after five months for the final prosthesis. At 5 months, the temporary crown was removed, impression coping was connected to the implant fixture, and the final impression was made using putty and light body using a closed tray technique. The implant analogue was then attached to the impression coping. Shade selection was done, and the impression was sent to the lab for the final zirconia prosthesis. After occlusal adjustments, the final prosthesis was cemented using type II GIC as a luting agent. The patient was kept on regular follow-up visits.

Preoperative CBT

Preoperative CBT

Digital Planning

Digital Planning

Discussion

Implant placement and loading protocols are pivotal components in dental implant treatment planning. Traditionally, implants were placed in fully healed edentulous sites, typically after six months of healing^[10]. However, this delayed protocol often led to extended treatment times and esthetic challenges due to alveolar bone resorption following extraction^[10].

Studies comparing immediate and early placement in anterior sites have shown comparable outcomes in ridge preservation, esthetics, and patient satisfaction^[11]. However, immediate implants have been associated with a higher incidence of mid-facial mucosal recession affecting up to 26% of cases^[12] with an average recession of 0.85 mm versus only 0.06 mm for early implants^[13]. Early implant placement allows for soft tissue healing, often resulting in a significantly thicker mucosal flap up to sevenfold in cases with thin or damaged facial walls thereby improving vascularity and reducing the need for grafting procedures^[14]. Additionally, this approach facilitates the formation of 2–3 mm of keratinized mucosa due to spontaneous healing and apical bone regeneration^[10]. Clinical studies have reported stable peri-implant soft tissue conditions for over three years with this technique^[8].

Immediate loading, defined as placing a prosthesis in occlusion within 48–72 hours post-surgery^[15,16], has shown comparable implant survival rates and marginal bone levels when compared with early loading protocols over 1–3 years. Given patient preference for shorter treatment times, immediate or early loading should be considered when clinical conditions are favorable^[17]. In the case presented, early implant placement with immediate loading was performed in the mandibular anterior region. A xenograft (Bio-Oss®) was used to fill the jumping gap, but no barrier membrane was applied. This simplified the procedure, reduced surgical time and cost, and maintained the regenerative capacity of the periosteum an essential source of mesenchymal stem cells, vascular supply, and growth factors crucial for bone healing^[18]. The clinical outcome showed excellent esthetic and functional results: no soft tissue recession, no vertical bone loss at six months, and well maintained peri-implant tissue in all directions. Both intraoral and extraoral soft tissues are vital in achieving optimal esthetics, and early implant placement plays a crucial role in preserving these tissues.

Despite its advantages, early implant placement does have limitations, such as increased surgical time and complexity compared to immediate placement. Still, it offers a slightly higher first year survival rate 98.3% versus 94.6% for immediate placement with immediate loading.

Conclusion

Early implant placement following soft tissue healing involves a healing period of 4–8 weeks after tooth extraction before implant insertion. This approach is particularly suitable when the facial

bone wall is thin or compromised, and the local bone morphology permits accurate three-dimensional implant positioning with adequate primary stability. It helps prevent vertical tissue collapse around the implant, promotes the formation of keratinized tissue on all sides, and allows for easier apical anchorage. The use of a surgical guide can further enhance the digital workflow in guided implant placement, improving precision and efficiency. Nonetheless, additional research is necessary to validate the potential benefits and clinical effectiveness of this emerging technique.

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